

Understanding Social Development of Girl Child through Education from Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV)

Laxmi Narayan Nayak

ABSTRACT

Democratic India with her constitutional commitments had targeted to offer justice to the marginalized sections through welfare measures and development initiatives. Education is one of the major sectors to bring social transformation. Among the excluded and deprived social groups, the condition of the girl child remained always worse than the boys. Education can bring greater participation of women in family, social, economic and political matters. The paradigm of social development is well achieved through education. It is commonly said that teaching a woman means teaching a family, so by educating women, we can propel society towards development. The Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) scheme is a step forward in this direction. The immense potential of the scheme helps in recovering the losses that girls faced in being pushed out of formal schools due to multiple reasons. The implication of this scheme is to provide a second chance for dropout girls to explore their possibilities towards empowerment. Primary data from a KGBV in the Deogarh district of Odisha was collected for the study. The present study thus is an attempt to focus on how KGBV brings on social development among girl children. It is found that girls debarred from education due to distance from school had been brought to the educational fold following the selection criteria of KGBV, and are satisfied with the facilities provided in the KGBV. Satisfaction helps in building their aspirations for the future which contributes to their process for social development.

Keywords: Girl child, Education, Aspiration, Satisfaction, Social development

Author Details:

Laxmi Narayan Nayak is a Ph.D. Research Scholar in the Department of Anthropology, Sambalpur University, Burla, Email: b4bapi85@gmail.com

I. INTRODUCTION

India has the second largest education system in the world after China (IER, 2005). Despite this, inefficiency is seen in education system due to various factors like vacancy in teaching position, infrastructure, non-teaching workforce, etc. contrary to the several schemes projected by the governments at both centre and state levels. Gupta (2014) had discussed and found illiteracy and ignorance as the important factors causing poverty in a developing country like India. Thus the role of education is very important in bringing a transformation. Education, besides enhancing general awareness, refines communication skills and provides opportunities for better vocational development which may improve the quality of

Suggested Citation:

Nayak (2023). Understanding Social Development of Girl Child through Education from Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV), *Journal of Studies in Dynamics and Change (JSDC)*, 10(4). 13-22.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10694222>

Published on: 01 October 2023

life. Parameters like growth in literacy rate, level of education, growth of educational institutions, enrolment by level of education, dropouts of students at school level, etc. determine educational status. The role of infrastructure available (building and classrooms), student classroom ratio, teacher pupil ratio, academic qualification of teachers, facilities like, drinking water, toilet and blackboard also play vital role in transformation of education.

The percentage growth of literacy in India in 2011 is 9.24 % whereas that of Odisha is 15.57% (Census of India, 2011). The literacy rate in India as per 2011 Census is 73%, with male literacy rate of 80.9% and female literacy rate of 64.60%. Further the literacy rate in Odisha by 2011 Census is 72.9%, with male literacy rate of 81.6% and that of females at 64.6%. In gender gap, Meghalaya has the lowest rate of 3 with Rajasthan having the highest of 27. Odisha shares the 5th position in gender gap with the rate of 18 (NSSO & Registrar General of India). The sex ratio and child sex ratio of Odisha are 978 and 934 respectively. This is better than the national rate, still the condition of our girl children belonging to economically poor, scheduled caste, scheduled tribe backgrounds, physically and mentally or otherwise challenged, displaced due to development projects and natural disasters, and victims of communal riots, is pitiable on a number of grounds.

According to the Statistical Abstract of Odisha (2012), the overall dropout rates in primary schools of Odisha in 2011-12 is 0.43, with female dropout rate (0.62) being higher than male dropout rate (0.25), whereas the dropout rate of SCs is 2.41 and that of STs is found to be 3.10. The overall dropout rates in upper primary schools of Odisha in 2011-12 is 3.07, with female dropout rate (2.23) being lower than male dropout rate (3.85), whereas the dropout rate of SCs is 2.74 and that of STs is found to be 4.70. Further it is found that the female dropout rate (1.23) among SCs is lower than male (2.20) but the female dropout rate (6.31) among STs is higher than that of male dropout rate (3.20). The overall dropout rates in high schools of Odisha in 2011-12 is 49.5, with a higher female dropout rate (51.8) than male dropout rate (47.2), whereas the dropout rate of SCs is found to be 60.5 and that of STs to be 64.3. It has also been found that the female dropout rate (61.8) among SCs is higher than male (59.2) but the female dropout rate (62.7) among STs is lower than that of male dropout rate (65.9) (OSEPA & DSE).

Social development of girl child has been explored by scholars and can be judged within the various parameters such as involvement of women in decision making process, freedom of choice and mobility, raising their voice against gender violence and empowerment through economic development. To identify and overcome such problems, several constitutional directives and recommendations have been provided by different committees and commissions from time to time. The New Education Policy of 1986 was expected to bring change and equal opportunity to girls through compulsory and free education to all up to the age of 14. Different government schemes have been launched for this purpose and while a few contributed some degree of social transformation, some others are languishing. Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) is one such scheme run by the central government.

Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV) is a scheme launched in July 2004, for setting up residential schools at upper primary level for girls predominantly belonging to the SC, ST, OBC and minority communities. The scheme is being implemented in Educationally Backward Blocks (EBB) of the country where the female rural literacy is below the national average and gender gap in literacy is

above the national average. The scheme provides for a minimum reservation of 75% of the enrolment for girls from SC, ST, OBC or minority communities. For the remaining 25%, priority is accorded to girls from families below poverty line. During the Tenth Five Year Plan period it was decided to have pattern of financing share with 75:25 ratio between the centre and the states respectively.

The main objectives of the Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya scheme are to facilitate retention of girls; to ensure greater participation of girls in education; to develop and promote facilities by providing access and quality education to girls belonging to disadvantaged groups like SC and ST by setting up residential schools at upper primary level; and to improve quality of education, especially the quality of girls' education for their empowerment.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

India has achieved about 70% literacy. But the rate of literacy among these marginalized sections is much lower when compared to other forward sections (Gandhi, 2015). According to Gupta (2014), illiteracy and ignorance are the important factors causing poverty in a developing country like India and the role of education is very important in bringing a transformation. Barar, et al., (2013), advocated education of women in India has gone in an undirected growth. Gender inequality in education has become an aspect of educational disparity. A girl child has to face many types of discrimination even within the family which obstacle the path of her development. Dropout rate is more among girls than boys. Reasons for dropout are various like, parents with meagre income consider only son's education, girls are looked upon as "*paraya-dhan*", stereotypical approach towards girls (focusing primarily on marriage), parents' reluctance to send their girls to co-educational schools, gender inequality interlocks with other social inequality i.e. caste, community, tribe, culture, religion, etc. as hurdles. There are several discrimination like access to only a small and limited social circle, denied from private tuition, boys sent to private schools whereas girl to government (public) schools, girls considered as child bearing and rearing machines, majority suffers from "deprivation syndrome" i.e. denied of tender loving care. On a different note, Dey (2015), using 66th round of National Sample Survey (2009-10) data reveals that work participation rate (WPR) among highly educated women are much lower in comparison to illiterate women in both rural and urban areas. Gender inequality persists and is highest among those who have up to higher secondary level of education.

The SCs and STs in India also remain cast away from the benefits of education. The condition has been the same during the British India due to their denial to mainstream education by the upper caste. After Independence, various constitutional amendments and privileges have been provided to them, still their educational status remains more or less the same. The factors that determine their access to primary or higher education are socio-economic characteristics (Singh, 1989 and Ghose, 2009) like occupation and education of parents, housing pattern, privileged families namely, literate homes (Chitnis, 1975); and traditional prejudices like caste (Kirpal, 1978) and untouchability (Benjamin, 1991). Chitnis (1975) further vowed that these special programmes for the educational development of the SCs and STs are giving rise to new inequalities within their castes whereas according to Malik (1979) developmental measures have aided social mobility among the scheduled castes to some extent. Jain (1981) advocated education to be poor's most potent weapon for self-advancement while Kumar (1983) argument that education introduces bourgeois values among the oppressed by curbing their

radical expression as education is perceived from the point of view of non-SC and ST educators .

Abdulraheem (2011) stated education as an important parameter for inclusive growth in an economy. According to Das (2009), language barrier of the tribal children made them unable to establish communication link with the teacher which leads towards their termination from education in some point or the other. Sujatha (2002) puts forth that formal education is not a critical demand among Scheduled Tribes. Behera (2015) has interpreted that education is the most powerful weapon and key to tribal development. Government policy focuses on education as the main avenue to integrate them into mainstream society. Jha and Jhingram (2002) advocated the use of the mother tongue as the language for medium of instruction in early stages of education in the context of education for tribal children because their mother tongue is often quite distinct from the well-known or popular language. On the other hand, Singh and Ohri (1993) emphasize that the role of modernization in education has improved the status of tribal.

III. OBJECTIVES

- To find out the aspiration of girl child through learning from KGBV
- To find out the perception of parents and students towards KGBV
- To identify how aspiration through KGBV builds up social development among girl children

IV. METHODOLOGY

The present study utilizes primary data to find its purpose. The study focuses on the indicators like the status of KGBV, facilities in KGBV and perception of parents. One KGBV is randomly selected from Deogarh district. 70 students are selected randomly from class 6th to 10th in the said KGBV. Perception of 30 parents has also been taken regarding KGBV.

V. ANALYSIS

Background of the Study

The root of inequality and disparity in education system starts at the base. Further Bagh (2015), mentioned that government schools are in a silent crisis, failing to

Figure-1: Selection Criteria of the Students

Source: Compiled by author from the field study

provide quality education at elementary level. Girl children are found to be more vulnerable and exposed to the problem of social exclusion due to various factors, one among them being education. This follows up with their high dropout rate and low literacy rate. The exclusionary processes include social, economic, political, and cultural aspects which has made it difficult for their access to education. In order to achieve inclusive growth and social development, the schemes for elementary education need to be streamlined and updated.

Figure-1 reveals the criteria in which the sample children are selected in the KGBV. The children with distance of more than 3 km from nearby school are put in the criteria of distance to get selected in the KGBV. It shows that the highest number of children fall in this criterion (62.86% of the total children). The children of single parent hold the 2nd highest percentage of 22.86% among the children. The other two criteria of selection are, children with poor economic condition, and dropout from previous school, which show 12.86% and 1.42% respectively.

Figure-2: Category-wise Classification

Source: Compiled by author from the field study

Figure-2 shows the caste-wise distribution of the girl children selected in the KGBV. The girl children belonging to ST category are more in number with 38.57% of total girl children, followed by girls belonging to SC category with 32.86%, and girls from OBC with 24.28%. The girl children of general category are the least with 4.29% of the total girl children taken for study.

Figure-3: Aspiration for Future

Source: Compiled by author from the field study

Figure-3 shows the aspiration of the girl children that they want to be in future. Majority of the children wanted to be a teacher (24.29%). Aspiration to be a nurse and doctor are 7.14% and 15.71% respectively. The percentage of children aspiring to be police is 14.29% whereas 15.71% children wanted to join armed forces. Ambition of 22.86% girl children is to be an artiste of any form as actor, dancer or singer, or to become a sports person.

Figure-4: Various Facilities as Required by the Inmates to Improve in the KGBV (in Nos.)

Source: Compiled by author from the field study

Requirement portrays the satisfaction from the available facility. More requirements may indicate lower satisfaction from the facilities and thus need for improvements. Figure-4 shows the requirement for improvement in facilities of the KGBV in accordance to the inmates. 72.86% inmates required the infrastructure to be improved, such as proper boundary wall, proper kitchen and dining, and number of rooms for inmates. According to 21.42% inmates, playground is required whereas

2.86% call for improvement in tuition facility as increase in number of tuition classes. For 1.43% inmates, facility of tube well would abridge their requirement.

Empirical Analysis of Logistic Regression Model

Table-1 shows the result for satisfaction (satisfied-1, not satisfied-0) of student or inmates with the facilities available in the KGBV. The satisfaction is taken as dependent variable and age of the students, criteria in which they are selected and their various requirements in KGBV are taken as the independent variables. The result shows that all the independent variables are statistically significant to predict the dependent variable at level of significance 0.01 and 0.05. It is found that age and criteria are significant at the level 0.05 whereas various requirements of inmates are statistically significant to predict the dependent variable at level of significance 0.01. It shows both age and criteria of the students are positively related with coefficient 0.54 and 1 respectively to the dependent variable.

Table-1: Interpretation of Binomial Logistic Regression Model

Variable	Coefficients	Std. Error	Z-Statistics	Prob.
C	-7.78909	4.013403	-1.94077	0.0523
Age	0.547411	0.286395	1.911382	0.0560*
Criteria	1.00536	0.525095	1.914626	0.0555*
Requirement	-0.38516	0.157479	-2.44579	0.0145**

Source: Compiled from Field Report

Note: ** & *: indicates significant at 1% & 5% level of significance respectively

(Dependent variable: Satisfaction)

This means with increase in age of the inmates, more satisfaction is observed with the service provided in the KGBV. The other independent variable, criteria for selecting children is also positively related thus the criteria in which the girl child is selected in maximum i.e. distance from nearby school are found to be more satisfied with the facilities thus provided in the KGBV premises. The requirement of inmates from KGBV is negatively related to predict dependent variable with coefficient -0.38, which means the inmates with highest requirement i.e. infrastructure are less satisfied with facilities in the KGBV.

Perception towards the Service Received from KGBV

Table-2: Multi-nominal Logistic Regression Result

Variable	Coefficients	Std. Error	Z-Statistics	Prob.
Criteria	0.265113	0.354969	0.746862	0.4551
Requirement	-0.21055	0.111595	-1.88671	0.0592*
Age	0.29952	0.203324	1.473121	0.1407
Limit Points				
LIMIT_4:C(4)	2.654895	3.003073	0.884059	0.3767
LIMIT_5:C(5)	4.285325	3.03379	1.412532	0.1578

Source: Compiled from Field Report

Note: (Dependent variable: Behaviour of Service Provider)

The above depicts the multinomial response (5 point Likert Scale) of dependent variable with independent variables. It is found that all the independent variables are statistically insignificant to predict the dependent variable while requirements of sample inmates is statistically significant at 10% level of significance where $\beta_2 < 0$, meaning that less number of inmates following a particular requirement have strong prediction towards the behaviour of service provider in KGBV. Requirement of the inmates is negatively related with the dependent variable with coefficient value of -0.21. Age and criteria are insignificant to the behaviour of service provider in the KGBV. Educational attainments of a student always thrive through the behaviour of teacher. It is thus considered in the study as it defined the psychological perspective of the inmates availing services.

Table-3: Perception towards Facilities in the KGBV (%)

Facilities Available	Satisfied with Services		Improvement Required	
	Students	Parents	Students	Parents
1. Infrastructure	27.14	33.33	72.86	66.67
2. Nutritious Food	100	100	0	0
3. Tuitions Facilities (twice a day)	97.14	100	2.86	0
4. Physical Training	100	100	0	0
5. Vocational Education	98.57	100	1.43	0
6. Healthcare Service	100	66.67	0	33.33
7. Protective Environment	27.14	33.33	72.86	66.67

Source: Compiled from Field Report

Table-3 depicts the perception of students and parents about the facilities in the KGBV. The perception has been made with close ended questions. Both parents and students are totally satisfied (100%) with the nutritious food provided and the physical training given in the KGBV. The perception of all the parents (100%) towards the tuition facilities and vocational education is found to be satisfactory whereas the satisfaction in both the facilities is found with 97.14% and 98.57% students respectively. In healthcare facilities provided 100% students are satisfied whereas 33.33% parents suggested some improvements are required. The satisfaction towards the infrastructure and protective environment in the KGBV needs improvement according to 72.86% students and 66.67% parents.

Table-4: Parents Perspective to Continue Education of their Children

Parents allowing to pursue future study	Number of Parents
Would, despite of any circumstances	90%
Would, if facilities provided	10%

Source: Compiled from Field Report

The above Table reveals the perspective of parents of the girl children to allow their children for future or higher studies. 27 out of 30 parents (90%) said they would definitely pursue their child for higher studies despite any circumstances while the rest 3 (10%) would allow if facilities like KGBV are provided further.

VI. FINDINGS

The KGBV is providing all the basic necessities to boost education and to bring children to mainstream education system. The selection criteria followed by the KGBV is unbiased and irrespective of any communal preference. It follows the criteria as structured in the guidelines for the KGBVs. The staffs associated with the KGBV are cordial and encouraging to the inmates of the KGBV. The students of the KGBV have great aspiration for their future. They are basically inspired from the positive and friendly environment of the KGBV which is not only giving them a hope to build a good future but also negates their fear of being called unprivileged because of their family background. As we know that children always aspire to become what they see near them or what inspires them the most, the satisfaction from the KGBV molds their interest to have good aspiration for future. The advocacy for requirement may be a positive sign towards their quest to build a future. It may be called a psychological advantage. It is found that the girl children selected with the criteria of distance from their nearby school, are more satisfied with the facilities in the KGBV. This indicates they had an urge for education and good future and are in need for better scope, which is provided in KGBV. The aspiration of the girl child studied indicates that they know that their development is possible by the position they achieve in future. They understand that by economic empowerment they can be socially developed.

Aspiration can be fulfilled when they pursue higher education. Parents and their socio-economic condition play a vital role in education of girl child in special. As it is found that some of the parents (10%) would allow their child for higher education if the facility like KGBV is provided, it shows their willingness but at the same time their incapability. Thus the impact of a scheme like KGBV is to be understood and sponsored by the government to streamline the girls who are out of education system for various reasons.

Social development of a girl child is being measured through several factors such as their ability in decision making, participation in various activities, preparing for desired job, etc. It is found that attaining higher education and an established job has been the criteria to identify the actual social development as it empowers them with their involvement in various matters and also helps them in decision making.

VII. CONCLUSION

Social development is a continuous process in the perspective of social change. Social development should be continuous and progressive to bring positive outcomes. Girl child in the society is particularly a vulnerable section whose rights are compelled always by the male members, just as in Manusmriti the position of women is always defined to be suppressed and dependent. Though we are living in a modern society it seems that the concept of Manu still prevails as we can see examples of honour killing, female foeticide, pardah system, etc. Social development is not just material or economical but it should have moral values. Liberty and equality in gender is provided by various constitutional amendments but its sustainability is maintained through social attributes such as giving equal space to women in various spheres, independency in decision making and participation in different activities. The term social development of a girl child is not mere eradication of discrimination rather it is a holistic approach. Education is one such parameter which empowers a girl child to attain social development. The higher the education of girl child, the higher is her aspiration. Aspiration may not be always material or successful still it gives a glimpse of social development. Various schemes

have been implemented by centre and state government to improve the social development of girl child. KGBV is such a flagship programme under the government which helps a girl child to bounce back through education. Though various changes need to be adopted, still KGBV acts as a stepping stone towards social development of a girl child.

VIII. REFERENCES

- Abdulraheem, A. (2011). Education for the Economically and Social Disadvantaged Groups in India: An Assessment. *Economic Affairs*, 56(2), June, 233-242.
- Bagh, S. (2015). Education in the ear of Market Economy: Consequences and Challenges. *Man & Development*, XXXVII(2), Chandigarh: Centre For Research in Rural and Industrial Development, 87-102.
- Behera, Amulya (2015). Primary Education among the Tribal People of Mayurbhanj District of Odisha: an Evaluate Study. *International Journal of humanities and Social Science Invention*, 4(2), 43-54.
- Benjamin, J. (1991). Social Mobility among the Scheduled Castes in Bihar: A Case Study of Barh Block. *Social Action*, 41(4), 442-453.
- Brar, L., et al. (2013). Gender Equity In education: How Far Have We Reached?. *The Eastern Anthropologist*, 66(4), New Delhi: Serials Publications, 417- 434.
- Cheney, G, R., et al. (2005). *India Education Report: India Education Profile*. Retrieved from <http://www.ncee.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/10/India-Education-Report.pdf>
- Chitnis, S. (1975). Education of Scheduled Castes. *Journal of Higher Education*, 1(2), 167-178.
- Das, Atal Bihari (2009). Status of Education of Scheduled Tribes in KBK Districts of Orissa. *Orissa Review*, October, 38-50.
- Dey, A. (2015). Educational Attainment and Gender Inequality in labour market: The paradox of women's employment in India. *Man & Development*, XXXVII(4), Chandigarh: Centre For Research in Rural and Industrial Development, 27-42.
- Directorate of Secondary Education. *Achievements/Progress under Samagra Shiksha (Elementary) & KGBV*. Retrieved from <https://dseodisha.in>
- Gandhi, M. (2015). Problems of Education Among SCs, STs, BCs and Minority Children: Opportunities And Challenges. *Man In India*, 95(4). New Delhi: Serials Publications (p) Ltd, 951-1003.
- Ghose, B, N. (2009). Problems of Education of Scheduled Tribes and Scheduled Castes: A Case Study in Calcutta and Surroundings and Medinipur and Surrounding Areas. *Vanyajati*, VII (3), 28-35.
- Govt. of Odisha (2012). *Statistical Abstract of Odisha 2012*. Directorate of Economics and Statistics Odisha, Bhubaneswar.
- Gupta, S, K. (2014). Educational Transformation in India. *The Eastern Anthropologist*, 67(1-2), New Delhi: Serials Publications, 125-140.
- Jain, L, C. (1981). Emancipation of Scheduled Castes and Tribes: Some Suggestions. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 16(9), 325-332.
- Jha, M. and Jhingram, D. (2002). Elementary Education for the poorest and other Deprived Groups. New Delhi: Centre for Policy Research.

- Kirpal, V. (1978). Higher Education for the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 13(4-5), 165, 167-169.
- Kumar, K. (1983). Educational Experience of Scheduled Caste and Tribes. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 18 (36-37), 1566-1572.
- Malik, S. (1979). *Social Integration of Scheduled Castes*. New Delhi: Abhinav Publications.
- National Council of Educational Research and Training. *National Consultation of Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya*. Retrieved from <http://www.ncert.nic.in/html/pdf/announcement.pdf/>
- Odisha School Education Programme Authority. Status of Secondary Education in Odisha. Retrieved from <https://osepa.odisha.gov.in>
- Singh, P. (1989). *Problem of Education among Scheduled Castes*. New Delhi: Mittal Publications.
- Singh, S. and Ohri, J. (1993). Status of tribal Women in India. *Social Change*, December, 23(4), 21-26.
- Sujatha, K. (2002). Education Among Scheduled Tribes, in Govinda, R. (ed.), *India Education Report: A Profile of Basic Education*, New Delhi: Oxford University Press.